

Research Community Gateway

Build a Gateway to your community's open and linked research outcomes
Customized to your needs

FACTSHEET FOR RESEARCH COMMUNITY MANAGERS AND RESEARCHERS

What is **Research Community Gateway**?

Is a service developed by **OpenAIRE-Connect**, which fosters transparent evaluation of results and facilitates reproducibility of science for research communities by enabling a scientific communication ecosystem supporting exchange of research products (publications, data, software, methods) and links between them across communities and across content providers.

A Virtual Research Environment

An overlay platform making it easy to share, link, disseminate and monitor all your publications, data, software, methods. In one place.

Open Science in action

A time-saving bundle of services for researchers to effortlessly practice open science. An integral part of the European Open Science Cloud.

What is for?

Researchers can use the Community Gateway to:

SEARCH - Discover research products in your community

- A view of the OpenAIRE Graph configured by experts of your research community who want to help you out with the data and literature deluge.

DEPOSIT - Find a repository to deposit your research outcome

- Deposit or publish your research in Open Access
- Find the appropriate repository to deposit your research products of any type (publication, data, software, other) or to include in your data management plan

LINK - Help growing the record of research of your community:

- Link your research product with your community, funding, and other research products.

Learn how in 4 steps

1 Understanding your needs

"Identify the scope and goals. Understand open science practices within EOSC and the OpenAIRE services."

In this stage, is where we meet and you share with the OpenAIRE Team your expectations and we give you all the details about the operational OpenAIRE services, which will be integrated into the Gateway for your community.

2 Develop a pilot

"We translate your needs into rules and processes and we configure operational OpenAIRE services."

Here we will set up a pilot Gateway, configuring the OpenAIRE mining algorithms to identify research products of the OpenAIRE Graph, that are relevant to your community. We'll also give you a demo of the Community Gateway to be customised.

3 Test and Validate

"You validate and test your new Community Gateway (portal). If needed, we further refine and adapt to your needs."

Here you'll test all its features. You can report us any issue you might find, then we configure the criteria for inclusion of the research products and wait for this new configuration to be applied in the OpenAIRE Graph. After that we validate the results and their suitability for the needs of the community.

4 Roll out the service

"We jointly roll out your new portal. You take over the business operations and start engaging your researchers."

Here we are: the coverage of research products is good, so we can roll out the Community Gateway and make it available to all the researchers of the community! Remember, you're not alone, you can always ask the OpenAIRE Team for support.

Benefits for Research Communities

Community-oriented Open Science publishing tools

Scientists can continue using RI services and publishing practices, but, if needed, can find support for publishing/interlinking any kind of products.

Collaborative curation of a community-specific scholarly communication information graph

An environment for the community to share, discover, interlink, gather and reuse (reproduce) scientific results. Powered by the OpenAIRE Graph.

Community-oriented Reporting and Open Science monitoring

Reporting to funders, development of scientific reward strategies inclusive of all products of science.

HOW COMMUNITY MANAGERS USE THE RESEARCH COMMUNITY GATEWAY

Manage Community

Edit community information, change logo url, add community managers

Adapt to your community identity

Configure the gateway according to the visual identity of your community

Manage Community Content

Select project grants, data sources, subjects and define other criteria to identify relevant research products among those in the OpenAIRE Graph

Manage links

Manage links added by community members.

Create your own menu

Link to other gateway pages or external web sites

We look forward to working together and helping you unlock the full potential of your research community through Open Science.

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

Other OpenAIRE services

<https://catalogue.openaire.eu/home>

For more information, please contact

info@openaire.eu

Useful Links

OpenAIRE Research Community Gateway

<https://connect.openaire.eu/>

OpenAIRE Support & Training materials

www.openaire.eu/support

OpenAIRE Research Community Gateway user guide

www.openaire.eu/research-community-gateway-guide

OpenAIRE Research Community Gateway video tutorials

https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL0c4IRNUxuKcyRUQ_J9BH_EE1amXU6kpg

Learn about Open Science Policies & how to align

<https://www.openaire.eu/toolkit-for-policy-makers-on-open-science-and-open-access>

Find out how to use OpenAIRE to best serve your needs

www.openaire.eu/guides

View our training materials on several topics

www.openaire.eu/support/webinars

This factsheet is also available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8189983>